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General Endodontic

GE52

Incidence of microcracks in maxillary first premolars after instrumentation with four endodontic file systems. A comparative ex-vivo study

Weissman A, Tesis I

Department of Endodontology, Tel Aviv University, Tel Aviv, Tel-Aviv, Israel

Aim Vertical root fractures (VRFs) may dramatically affect the long-term results of endodontic and restorative treatments. Micro-cracks in radicular dentin caused by rotary endodontic instrumentation, have been recently claimed to be a potential predisposing factor to VRFs. The aim of the study was to study the phenomenon of microcracks that might potentially be caused by mechanized instrumentation in first maxillary premolars.

Summary Intact extracted maxillary first premolars with two root canals were selected. None of the teeth had any externally visible microcracks when checked with small diameter light source under x20 magnification. Root canal mechanized instrumentation was performed with either the ProTaper file system, a WaveOne primary file or the Self-adjusting File (SAF). Teeth with intact roots and teeth that were treated with hand K files served as controls. The roots were then cut into segments and examined with an intensive small diameter light source that was applied diagonally to the entire periphery of the root slice, under x20 magnification; the presence of microcracks was recorded. Statistical analysis was performed using Pearson's Chi-square method, with 0.05 set as the significance level. Microcracks were found in 30% and 20% of the ProTaper and WaveOne treated roots, respectively. No microcracks were found in the SAF treated roots, while the intact control group and the hand file treated groups presented with cracks in 5% and 10% of the roots, respectively. The intensive small diameter light source revealed microcracks that could not be detected when using the microscope's light alone

Key Learning Points

- Mechanized root canal instrumentation with ProTaper and WaveOne in maxillary first premolars caused microcracks in the radicular dentin, while the use of the SAF file caused no such microcracks.
- An intensive small diameter light source should be used

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Resistance to cyclic fatigue of two different sized rotary nickel-titanium instruments in artificial canals

*Stojanac I, Premovic M, Ramic B, Drobac M, Petrovic LJ

Department of dentistry, Medical faculty, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

Aim The aim of this study is to investigate the resistance to cyclic fatigue of two different sized rotary nickel-titanium instruments in the artificial canals with two different curvatures.

Methodology The total sample consisted of 40 rotary endodontic nickel-titanium instruments (20 ProTaper F1 I 20 ProTaper F2) was divided into four groups . Ten samples of both type of instruments were tested in canals with smaller curvature (27 degree and 40 mm radius angle) and ten samples in the canals with grater curvature (35 degree and 13 mm radius angle) at a speed stated in the manufacturer instructions. Two artificial canals were fabricated in stainless steel blocks according to the curvature parameters chosen for this study. This canals were conical shape corresponding to the taper and the diameter of the studied Ni-Ti instruments. Rotation period of instruments in the artificial canal was 10 seconds, after which it was stopped and removed from the canal to cool down in the following 10 seconds. Than it was again placed in the canal and being rotated for 10 seconds until instrument separation and that was numerically noted in seconds by chronometar.

Results In contrast to canals with a larger degree of curvature (35°-13mm), the examined instruments in the canals with a smaller degree of curvature (27°-40mm) showed higher resistance

to cyclic fatigue. The greater resistance to cyclic fatigue in the canals of both degrees of curvature was shown by F1 instruments which had higher average number of cycles to fracture appearance. **Conclusions** The instrument with smaller dimension (F1) showed higher resistance to cyclic fatigue regardless of the curvature degree. The taper of instruments have influence on resistance of rotary NiTi instruments to cyclic fatigue, and instruments with grater taper have lower resistance to cyclic fatigue.

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Impact of Experience on cyclic fatigue of Revo-s Rotary instruments

*ÖVSAY EO, Kazandağ Karapınar MK, Kaptan FK

Department of Endodontics, Yeditepe University Faculty Of Dentistry, Istanbul, Turkey

Aim To evaluate the cyclic fatigue fracture resistance of engine-driven Revo-S instruments used by dental students, residents and endodontists.

Methodology A sample of 90 size 25, 0.08 taper Revo-S instruments used by students (n=30), residents (n=30) and endodontists (n=30) were tested. Each group were divided into 3 subgroups (n=10) to be tested in simulated canals with 60, 45, 90 angle of curvature and a 3 mm radius at a constant speed 350rpm and 0.8nm torque until they were fractured. The time of fracture for each instrument was recorded. The data was compared using one-way analysis of variance followed by Tukey's Honestly Significant Different test.

Results The instruments used by undergraduate students resulted in a significantly longer cyclic fatigue life ($P < 0.0001$) when compared the ones used by residents or endodontists. No difference of cyclic fatigue was found between residents and endodontists

Conclusions The dental students caused less cyclic fatigue than residents and endodontists. Multiple use of size 25, 0.08 taper Revo-S instruments maybe more favorable in undergraduate than residency or specialist clinics.

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Effect of Protaper Universal, Self adjusting file, Twisted file adaptive and Reciproc rotary instrument on microcrack Formation in Dentin

Fundaoglu Kucukekenci F¹, Cakici F¹, Cakici EB¹, *Kucukekenci AS²

Departments of ¹Endodontics, ²Prosthodontics, Faculty of Dentistry, Ordu, Turkey

Aim To investigate the effect of instrumentation kinematics on incidence of microcracks in root dentin during root canal instrumentation with Twisted File adaptive (SybronEndo,Orange,CA) ,self-adjusting file(SAF) (ReDent-Novaltd, Ra'anana, Israel),ProTaper Universal(PTU) (Dentsply Maillefer,Ballaigues, Switzerland) and Reciproc (VDW GbmH) rotary instruments.

Methodology One hundred – eight mandibular premolars were selected. Eighteen teeth were left unprepared and served as a control. The remaining ninety teeth were randomly divided five groups(n= 18). Group 1: TF Adaptive()instrumentation, group 2: SAF instrumentation, group 3: PTU instrumentation, group 4: reciproc instrumentation , group 5 Protaper Universal F2 file in reciprocating motion. After the root canal preparation all the roots were sectioned perpendicular to the long axis at 3,6 and 9 mm from the apex using a low-speed saw under water cooling, and the sections were observed under a stereomicroscope at a magnification of $\times 250$.

Results No microcracks were observed in the control grup. Vertical root fractures were not observed in any of the groups. All of the instrumentation system used in this study created microcracks in the root dentin. In root prepared with PTU, Reciproc, SAF, F2 in Reciprocating motion and TFA, dental microcrack were observed in 13%, 9%, %8, %6 and %2 of teeth.In the present study, the occurrence of microcrack formations in the coronal thirds was %7.4, %3.7 in the middle thirds, and % 1.48 in the apical thirds.Fewer microcrack formations occurred in apical thirds than middle and coronal thirds.